

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCE

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CHAT GPT AS A LEARNING TOOL IN EDUCATION

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CHAT GPT КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ ОБУЧЕНИЯ В ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

Abstract:

This article deals with the popular learning electronic resource Chat GPT among the students. It's known that, technology has become a driving force behind innovation and transformation in short times. The scientific purpose of AI, especially Chat GPT its similarity to living human consciousness, the work that it can do in the future, and the effects created by robots in society are discussed in this article. The concept of human and Chat GPT, the understanding of the language based on the request in short period and the result created by artificial intelligence are reflected in this scientific article. The article also quotes scientists who predicted these facts 30 years ago. The goal of the artificial intelligence, artificial systems of the human mind, thinking and brain, connection with other subjects are analyzed in this article.

Nowadays people of any age prefer search for all the necessary information on the Internet, using specifically developed program. However, they do not always get what they are looking for. So, for example, when trying to translate text or a phrase from one language to another using you can often get an inadequate and incorrect translation from an online translator. Finding the right solutions to a query written in natural language, is a whole science. And this science is computational linguistics, which deals with drawing up such programs.

Аннотация:

В данной статье рассматривается популярный обучающий электронный ресурс Chat GPT среди студентов. Известно, что технологии за короткое время стали движущей силой инноваций и преобразований. В этой статье обсуждаются научная цель ИИ, особенно Chat GPT, его сходство с живым человеческим сознанием, работа, которую он может выполнять в будущем, а также эффекты, создаваемые роботами в обществе. В этой научной статье отражены концепция GPT человека и чата, понимание языка на основе запроса в короткие сроки и результат, создаваемый искусственным интеллектом. В статье также цитируются учёные, предсказавшие эти факты 30 лет назад. В статье анализируется цель искусственного интеллекта, искусственные системы человеческого разума, мышления и мозга, связь с другими предметами.

Сегодня люди любого возраста предпочитают искать всю необходимую информацию в Интернете, используя специально разработанную программу. Однако они не всегда получают то, что ищут. Так, например, при попытке перевести текст или фразу с одного языка на другой при помощи онлайн-переводчика вы часто можете получить неадекватный и неправильный перевод. Найти правильные решения запроса, написанного на естественном языке, — целая наука. И эта наука — компьютерная лингвистика, которая занимается составлением таких программ.

Ключевые слова: ИИ, электронный словарь, программное обеспечение, Chat GPT

Key-words: AI, e-dictionary, software, chat GPT

Introduction: Modern linguistics conducts continuous research on the study of the advantages of electronic translation and the further development of this field in the future. The fact that linguists have recently turned to electronic dictionaries is related to the emergence of a large number of electronic dictionaries on the Internet and the increase in the number of their use. Electronic dictionaries are types of dictionaries arranged in alphabetical order and consisting of innovative search techniques. These types of dictionaries are more portable and easily accessible, most of them are free and constantly updated. The virtual nature of online dictionaries is volatile, their local address (URL) location may change at any time, or they may be removed permanently. Searches in electronic dictionaries search the query word in a limited way based on the

main word (or word root), but the information is presented in lexicographic norms (key words, phrases, synonyms, antonyms, dictionary articles). Searches can be precise or fuzzy. Users select the one that matches or is simply similar to the word they have identified. In electronic dictionaries, the word presentation form does not end with a single alphabetical order, the principles of word presentation are different in each electronic dictionary. It is known that the Internet is constantly developing, dictionaries often change their structure, and the presentation form of a dictionary often changes.

Unfortunately, to date linguists have not identified a universal model of language that could be applied to any language material. The same request can be interpreted in different ways and given different meanings. Language processing requires sequential analysis, the

stages of which correspond to the levels of language structure. And all the programmer needs are to implement the sequence of analysis stages. To visually represent this sequence, we will provide an explanation for each of its levels that the programmer needs to go through. Themes that we mentioned above are analyzed by relating AI capabilities in this article. Beside this, similarities and differences of the system are shown.

INTRODUCTION: The term "intelligent system" means a technology or software system stored in the memory of that system, capable of solving problems traditionally characterized as a creative process. Many studies have been conducted and research works have been written on the history of the creation of artificial intelligence, its essence, the importance of application areas and development prospects. The goal of the artificial intelligence science is the creation of artificial systems that can imitate the human mind, thinking and brain. In the formation of artificial intelligence as a science, mathematics, physics, biology, physiology, biotechnology, computer science, psychology, philosophy, logic, linguistics, economics, etc. sciences play an important role. One of the most important areas of artificial intelligence is natural language processing.

Among the many cutting-edge technologies making waves in the educational landscape, Chat GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer) has emerged as a powerful tool for transforming learning experiences through AI conversations. Chat GPT was developed by OpenAI, an artificial intelligence research lab founded in December 2015. The team behind OpenAI consisted of prominent individuals such as Elon Musk, Sam Altman, Greg Brockman, Ilya Sutskever, Wojciech Zaremba, and John Schulman. ChatGPT is a language model developed by OpenAI, and its part of the GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer) series. In the specific version GPT robot based on GPT-3.5.

In this comprehensive article, we delve deep into the applications, advantages, and future potential of Chat GPT in education. Let's explore how this revolutionary technology is reshaping the way we learn and interact with information.

1. **GPT-3 Release (June 2020):** Open AI released GPT-3, the third iteration of the Generative Pre-trained Transformer. It gained attention for its impressive language generation capabilities, having been trained on a diverse range of internet text.

2. **ChatGPT Release (November 2021):** Open AI introduced ChatGPT as a sibling model to GPT-3. It was fine-tuned using Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF) to generate more coherent and contextually relevant responses in a conversation format.

Function:

ChatGPT is designed for natural language understanding and generation. It can perform a variety of language tasks, including answering questions, providing information, generating creative content, and engaging in conversation.

Role in Education: ChatGPT can play a significant role in education in several ways:

1. **Tutoring and homework assistance:** ChatGPT can assist students by answering questions, providing explanations, and offering help with homework or assignments.

2. **Language Learning:** Students learning a new language can use ChatGPT to practice conversational skills, receive language tips, and get instant feedback.

3. **Research assistance:** ChatGPT can be a valuable tool for researchers and students conducting literature reviews, generating ideas, and obtaining information on various topics.

4. **Programming Assistance:** Students studying programming can use ChatGPT to seek clarification on coding concepts, get help with debugging, and explore new programming languages.

5. **Creative Writing Support:** Aspiring writers and students can leverage ChatGPT to generate ideas, receive feedback on writing, and overcome creative blocks.

It's important to note that while ChatGPT can be a useful tool in education, it should complement traditional learning methods and be used responsibly. Educators and students can benefit from incorporating AI like ChatGPT as an additional resource to enhance the learning experience. OpenAI has also provided guidelines and safety measures to ensure responsible use of their models.

GPT has not a specific "lexic base capacity" in terms of the number of words or entries, it is based on a diverse range of sources available on the internet. I've been trained on a mixture of licensed data, data created by human trainers, and publicly available data. In this training also involved processing and learning from a vast amount of text from books, articles, websites, and other texts to develop a broad understanding of human language. However, it does not have access to specific databases or real-time information.

It has been trained on a diverse range of texts in multiple languages, so I have some degree of understanding of many languages. However, Chat GPT'S proficiency and accuracy vary across languages, and It is the most proficient in English. But if you have a specific language in mind, feel free to ask, and It'll do all best to assist you!

Chat GPT query mechanism involves processing and understanding the input text you provide and generating a relevant and coherent response. The mechanism is based on a deep neural network architecture called GPT-3.5, developed by OpenAI. It uses a transformer-based model that has been pre-trained on a diverse range of internet text. When you submit a query, the model analyzes the context, understands the relationships between words, and generates responses based on patterns and information it has learned during training. It doesn't have access to real-time information and relies on the knowledge it gained from its training data.

ChatGPT can be a helpful tool for students learning the English language. Here are several ways in which it can assist:

1. **Conversational practice:** Students can use ChatGPT to practice their conversational skills in English. Engaging in conversations with the model

can help improve fluency and comfort with the language.

2. **Grammar and Vocabulary:** ChatGPT can provide explanations and examples to help students understand grammar rules and expand their vocabulary. It can offer instant feedback on the correct usage of words and phrases.

3. **Writing Assistance:** Students working on writing assignments can use ChatGPT to get suggestions, ideas, and feedback on their writing. It can assist with sentence structure, coherence, and overall composition.

4. **Language Clarification:** If students come across words or phrases, they find confusing, they can ask ChatGPT for clarification. The model can provide definitions and context to enhance understanding.

5. **Cultural Context:** Learning a language involves understanding its cultural nuances. ChatGPT can provide information about English-speaking cultures, idioms, and expressions, adding a cultural dimension to language learning.

It's important to note that while ChatGPT can be a valuable supplementary tool for language learning, it should not replace traditional methods such as language classes, practice with native speakers, and immersive experiences. Additionally, as with any language learning tool, it's essential to use ChatGPT responsibly and critically, recognizing its limitations and seeking diverse learning opportunities.

The main aim of creating ChatGPT, and the GPT series in general, is to develop powerful and versatile language models that can understand and generate human-like text. OpenAI's goals in creating ChatGPT include:

1. **Advancing Natural Language Understanding:** OpenAI aims to push the boundaries of natural language understanding and generation. By developing models like ChatGPT, they seek to improve the ability of AI systems to comprehend and respond to human language in a more nuanced and contextually relevant manner.

2. **Building Conversational AI:** ChatGPT is specifically designed for conversational interactions. OpenAI aims to create AI systems that can engage in meaningful and coherent conversations, providing users with a more interactive and dynamic experience.

3. **Research and Development:** The development of models like ChatGPT contributes to ongoing research in the field of artificial intelligence and natural language processing. It helps researchers understand the capabilities and limitations of large-scale language models and drives innovations in the broader AI community.

4. **Providing Useful Applications:** OpenAI intends for models like ChatGPT to be useful in a variety of applications, ranging from assisting users in generating content to aiding in education, research, and problem-solving.

5. **Learning from User Interaction:** OpenAI often releases models like ChatGPT to the public as part of a research preview. Allowing users to interact with the model helps gather valuable feedback and insights, enabling further improvements and refinements.

It's important to note that while ChatGPT serves these aims, OpenAI also emphasizes responsible and ethical use of AI technologies. They provide guidelines and safety measures to ensure users engage with the model in a manner that aligns with ethical standards.

ChatGPT can perform some functions that are similar to electronic dictionaries, but it goes beyond the typical capabilities of a dictionary. Here are some ways in which ChatGPT's performance is comparable to and different from electronic dictionaries: Equal sides like as similarities are as follows:

Definitions and Explanations: Like a dictionary, ChatGPT can provide definitions and explanations for words and phrases. It can help users understand the meaning and usage of terms.

1. **Vocabulary Assistance:** ChatGPT can assist with expanding vocabulary by suggesting synonyms, antonyms, and related words, similar to how a dictionary might provide additional words.

2. **Language Clarifications:** Users can ask ChatGPT for clarifications on language-related queries, similar to consulting a dictionary for language-related doubts. Differences as follows:

1. **Conversational Interaction:** ChatGPT is designed for interactive and dynamic conversations. Users can engage in back-and-forth discussions, ask follow-up questions, and seek information in a more conversational manner, which goes beyond the static nature of traditional dictionaries.

2. **Contextual Understanding:** ChatGPT excels at understanding context and generating responses that take into account the broader conversation. It can provide information and explanations in a contextually relevant manner.

3. **Application Beyond Definitions:** While dictionaries primarily focus on providing definitions, ChatGPT can go beyond that by generating detailed explanations, offering examples in context, and assisting with various language-related tasks, such as writing assistance and language learning.

E-library: Digital or Software Library:

- In the context of computer science and information technology, the term "library" refers to a collection of pre-written code, routines, or functions that can be used by software developers to simplify the development of software applications.

- These libraries can include modules, classes, or functions that perform specific tasks, and developers can integrate them into their own programs to avoid reinventing the wheel and save time.

- Examples of software libraries include standard libraries in programming languages like Python or Java, as well as specialized libraries for tasks such as graphics, networking, or data processing.

f.eg. <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/library?q=library>

The meaning of "library" can vary based on the field or context in which it is used, but it generally refers to a collection of resources or information organized for easy access and use. F.eg.

a building in which collections of books, newspapers, etc. and sometimes films and recorded music are kept for people to read, study or borrow

- *a public/university/school library*
- *a library book*
- *a toy library* (= for borrowing toys from)
- *How often do you go to the library?*

Finally, ChatGPT can perform certain functions reminiscent of electronic dictionaries, it offers a more versatile and interactive experience due to its conversational nature and contextual understanding capabilities. It's not a replacement for a traditional dictionary but can be a valuable tool for a range of language-related tasks.

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